

Research Article**The effects of Federalism on Peacemaking in Mogadishu – Somalia.**Mahdi Abdirizak Keynan¹, Ahmenur Mohamed Jama²

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Abstract

The concept of federalism is not new but is still quite vague in developing countries. Somalia is the most failed state in the world after more than two decades of civil war and inter-clan conflict, which lead many Somalis to be refugee in all over the world, but know International community are supporting to see Somalia back in the world, which federalism is the corner stone of reconciliation and development, and peacemaking thought Somalia constitution is based Federal system which was agreed by Somalis in 2004, when The Transitional Federal was established as one of the Transitional Federal Institutions (TFIs) of government as defined in the Transitional Federal Charter (TFC) adopted in November 2004 by the Transitional Federal Parliament (TFP). The Aim of this study is to determine and examine the effects of federalism on peacemaking, whether it has positive or negative relationship or not. Both qualitative and quantitative research design was used in this study to explore the effects of Federalism on Peacemaking, Mogadishu, Somalia. Majority of the respondents 48% who were asked questions replied that federalism has not contributed peacemaking within Mogadishu, Somalia, while 22% of the respondents did not. 36% of respondents are strongly disagreed that federalism has contributed unity of the country, while 16% of the respondents agreed that federalism has contributed. 46% replied that peace brings rule of law, while 4% of the respondents mentioned that peace did not contribute rule of law. According to the data collected from the respondents indicates that there is less power sharing so it is highly recommended that: There must be fair division of powers in order federalism to lead peacemaking in Mogadishu-Somalia. The researcher also recommended orienting and teaching the community members and community leaders to understand federalism contributing on peacemaking in Mogadishu Somalia.

Keywords: *Federalism, Peace Making, Governance, Decentralization, Mogadishu-Somalia.*

Introduction

The concept of federalism has been defined by many scholars in different ways; Where defines federalism as “a system in which two levels of government-federal and regional (state) exist side by side, with each possessing certain assigned powers and functions.”. In this study we focused on this Federalism Can be defined as the system of “self-rule plus shared rule, provides for power sharing, cuts around the issue of sovereignty, and supplements but does not seek to replace or diminish prior organic ties where they exist, Daniel Elazar (1987)

According to Elazar (1987b) and Ostrom (1989), the term “Federalism” originated from the Latin term “Foedus”, meaning “Covenant”. For Börzel (n.d) federalism “refers to a spatial or territorial division of power between two or more levels of government in a given political system”.) Therefore, federalism is “a political organization in which the activities of government are divided between regional governments and a central government in such a way that each kind of government has some activities on which it makes final decisions.

The greatest success to-date for the federal principle is undoubtedly the US federal constitution, hammered out over the summer of 1787 at Philadelphia. Ultimately, this federal constitution enabled a continental-sized area to come under the control of a single democratic government, which previously would have been considered impossible (and was in fact considered impossible by the anti-federalists in 1787).

First, in the context of the contemporary global scene, federal political systems combining shared rule and self-rule do provide a practical way of combining the benefits of unity and diversity through representative institutions, but they are no panacea for humanity’s political ills. Second, the effectiveness of a federal political system depends on the degree of public acceptance of the need to respect constitutional norms and structures, and on a spirit of compromise and tolerance.

In Africa, federalism is associated with the colonial experience of divide and rule (Assefa 2007: 101). This means that in different contexts federalism can mean different things depending on the cultural and historical connotations. During Colonialism colonial rulers in Africa followed a unitary system of government in governing African colonies. The British had tried to introduce federalism in some of their colonies in Africa. However, African nationalists and anti-colonial leaders strongly resisted the British attempt, perceiving it as the continuation of “divide and rule” in another form. It was on this ground nationalist leaders such as Kwame Nkrumah of Ghana campaigned against federalism. After independence, the new African rulers opted for the unitary system of government (Agbu 2004: 30). The African leaders preferred the formation of a unitary governments rather than federalism (Jinadu Sep. 2002: 14-15). In contemporary Africa, most of the countries are unitary

states with political power vested in the central government (Kimenyi 1998: 43). Many political leaders in Africa at present are not willing to entertain federalism fearing that federalism reinforces tribalism (Kimenyi 1998: 61). As Elaigwu (1994: 76) opined the new rulers of post-colonialism Africa considered federalism as a crisis escalator rather than a crisis damper

Somalia is the most failed state in the world after more than two decades of civil war and inter-clan conflict, which lead many Somalis to be refugee in all over the world, but know International community are supporting to see Somalia back in the world, which federalism is the corner stone of reconciliation and development, and peacemaking thought Somalia constitution is based Federal system which was agreed by Somalis in 2004, when The Transitional Federal was established as one of the Transitional Federal Institutions (TFIs) of government as defined in the Transitional Federal Charter (TFC) adopted in November 2004 by the Transitional Federal Parliament (TFP).

As a contextual, Somali choosing a new Stage which we may called “new federalism” because it reflects the return of administrative powers to the state governments, thought Elections in 2016 which the Essential to a sustainable process of institution building was the emergence of a definition of federalism that captures the aspirations and concerns of the people in various regions of Somalia, but Somalia faced and still facing many challenges among Somali political leader but defining Somalia’s federalism will require an accommodation with the political truths among all sides of Somalis and they have to have a common relationship in order for that nation to remain strong, Since federalism worked for the first republic in Somalia, it can still work again for us if properly implemented.. True federalism is the answer, for there to be a control to clan riots and civil unrest in the country, true federalism is the answer, because when the government of Mogadishu decides to implement fully the federalism, whole Somalis will adopt.

Objectives

The Aim of the study was to determine and examine the effects of federalism on peacemaking, whether it has positive or negative relationship or not. The main purpose is to clearly identify the impact of federalism in peacemaking, Mogadishu, Somalia.

Materials & Methods

The design was correlation both qualitative and quantitative research design was used in this study to explore the effects of Federalism on Peacemaking, Mogadishu, Somalia. Qualitative research is frequently used to describe and understand human behavior or experiences related to a particular phenomenon. Qualitative research draws on subjective data that is difficult to code numerically and focuses on feelings, experiences, and the content of people’s articulations. Therefore, in-depth

information and understanding regarding a phenomenon is best revealed using qualitative methods as they provide.

The study is also said to be correlation in design because there was intent to establish the relationship between the impact of federalism on peacemaking and this method was considered best for the research’s purpose.

Data Analysis & Interpretation

Section A: The demographic information of responder

1. Respondents by Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	BELOW 20	15	30.0	30.0	30.0
	20-30	35	70.0	70.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Primary source: The percentage of the respondents in between the age of 20 and 30 was 70% while those who are below 20 was 30%, this implies that respondents questioned were all mature enough to answer the questionnaire distributed to them.

2. Respondents’ by Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	MALE	38	76.0	76.0	76.0
	FEMALE	12	24.0	24.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Primary source: majority of the respondents 76% are male while 24% of respondents are female. Based on data gathered, the majority of the respondents are male, while a small number of the respondents are female.

3. Respondents’ by Marital Status

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	MARRIED	17	34.0	34.0	34.0
	UNMARRIED	33	66.0	66.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Primary source: Most of respondents are 66% are unmarried, while the remaining 34% of the respondents are married. Thus, this result showed that the majority of the respondents were Unmarried.

4. Respondents' by Qualification

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	MASTER	1	2.0	2.0	2.0
	BACHELAR	35	70.0	70.0	72.0
	DIPLOMA	10	20.0	20.0	92.0
	OTHERS	4	8.0	8.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Primary source: Majority of the respondents 70% were holding bachelor's degree and are mature enough, their answers are highly reliable. Thus, the answers collected from the respondents imply that they have enough information about both the negative and positive effects of federalism on peacemaking in Mogadishu, Somalia.

Section B: The Effect of Federalism on Peace Making

Federalism has contributed to an end to war for different people

Primary source: Majority of the respondent 19% answered that federalism has genuinely federal division power bring peace, while 12% of the respondents replied that federalism has not.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	STRONGLY DISAGREE	7	14.0	14.0	14.0
	DISAGREE	24	48.0	48.0	62.0
	NEUTRAL	4	8.0	8.0	70.0
	AGREE	11	22.0	22.0	92.0
	STRONGLY AGREE	4	8.0	8.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Primary source: Majority of the respondents 48% who were asked questions replied that federalism has not contributed peacemaking within Mogadishu, Somalia, while 22% of the respondents did not.

Federalism genuinely federal division of powers bring peace

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	STRONGLY DISAGREE	7	14.0	14.0	14.0
	DISAGREE	12	24.0	24.0	38.0
	NEUTRAL	1	2.0	2.0	40.0
	AGREE	19	38.0	38.0	78.0
	STRONGLY AGREE	11	22.0	22.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Federalism has contributed unity of the country

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	STRONGLY DISAGREE	18	36.0	36.0	36.0

DISAGREE	9	18.0	18.0	54.0
NEUTRAL	6	12.0	12.0	66.0
AGREE	8	16.0	16.0	82.0
STRONGLYAGREE	9	18.0	18.0	100.0

Total	50	100.0	100.0	
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Primary source: Majority 36% of respondents are strongly disagreed that federalism has contributed unity of the country, while 16% of the respondents agreed that federalism has contributed.

Peace there is rule of law

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	STRONGLYDISAGREE	3	6.0	6.0	6.0
	DISAGREE	2	4.0	4.0	10.0
	NEUTRAL	6	12.0	12.0	22.0
	AGREE	16	32.0	32.0	54.0
	STRONGLY AGREE	23	46.0	46.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Primary source: The majority of respondents 46% replied that peace brings rule of law, while 4% of the respondents mentioned that peace did not contribute rule of law.

Peace brings government closer to the people

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	STRONGLYDISAGREE	5	10.0	10.0	10.0
	DISAGREE	6	12.0	12.0	22.0
	NEUTRAL	2	4.0	4.0	26.0
	AGREE	17	34.0	34.0	60.0
	STRONGLYAGREE	20	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Primary source: Majority of the respondents 40% agreed that peace closes people to the government, while 12% of the respondents did not.

Peace Fair distribution of resources to the citizens

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	STRONGLYDISAGREE	8	16.0	16.0	16.0
	DISAGREE	2	4.0	4.0	20.0
	NEUTRAL	12	24.0	24.0	44.0
	AGREE	13	26.0	26.0	70.0
	STRONGLY AGREE	15	30.0	30.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Primary source: Majority of the respondents 30% were distributed questionnaires responded that peace makes fair distribution of resources to the citizens, while 16% of the respondents disagreed that.

Correlations			
		federalism	Peace
Federalism	Pearson Correlation	1	.341*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.015
	N	50	50
Peace	Pearson Correlation	.341*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.015	
	N	50	50

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Based on the result of the table above, the relationship between federalism and peacemaking Is investigated using Pearson product momentum correlation.

Discussion

Federalism as “a system in which two levels of government-federal and regional (state) exist side by side, with each possessing certain assigned powers and functions.”. Somalia is the most failed state in the world after more than two decades of civil war and inter-clan conflict, which lead many Somalis to be refugee in all over the world, but know International community are supporting to see Somalia back in the world, which federalism is the corner stone of reconciliation and development, and peacemaking thought Somalia constitution is based Federal system which was agreed by Somalis in 2004,when The Transitional Federal was established as one of the Transitional Federal Institutions (TFIs) of government as defined in the Transitional Federal Charter (TFC) adopted in November 2004 by the Transitional Federal Parliament (TFP).The findings obtained from the study demonstrated that The percentage of the respondents in between the age of 20 and 30 was 70% while those who are below 20 was 30%, majority of the respondents 76% are male while 24% of respondents are female, Majority of the respondents 70% were holding bachelor’s degree and are mature enough, their answers are highly reliable, Most of respondents are 66% are unmarried, while the remaining 34% of the respondents are married. Thus, this result showed that the majority of the respondents are Unmarried.

Majority of the respondents 48% who were asked questions replied that federalism has not contributed peacemaking within Mogadishu, Somalia, while 22% of the respondents did not.

Majority of the respondent 19% answered that federalism has genuinely federal division power bring peace, while 12% of the respondents replied that federalism has not.

Majority 36% of respondents are strongly disagreed that federalism has contributed unity of the country, while 16% of the respondents agreed that federalism has contributed.

The majority of respondents 46% replied that peace brings rule of law, while 4% of the respondents mentioned that peace did not contribute rule of law.

Majority of the respondents 40% agreed that peace closes people to the government, while 12% of the respondents did not. Majority of the respondents 30% were distributed questionnaires responded that peace makes fair distribution of resources to the citizens, while 16% of the respondents disagreed that. Based on the result of the table above, the relationship between federalism and peacemaking Is investigated using Pearson product momentum correlation Recommendations

From the findings of the study, the researchers recommended that:

According to the data collected from the respondents indicates that there is less power sharing so it is highly recommended that:

- ✓ There must be fair division of powers in order federalism to lead peacemaking in Mogadishu-Somalia.
- ✓ The researcher recommended orienting and teaching the community members and community leaders to understand federalism contributing on peacemaking in Mogadishu Somalia.

Conclusion

The concept of federalism is not new but is still quite vague in developing countries. The study aimed to see the effects of federalism on peacemaking in Mogadishu – Somalia. While Federalism as “a system in which two levels of government-federal and regional (state) exist side by side, with each possessing certain assigned powers and functions.”. Somalia is the most failed state in the world after more than two decades of civil war and inter-clan conflict, which lead many Somalis to be refugee in all over the world, but know International community are supporting to see Somalia back in the world, which federalism is the corner stone of reconciliation and development, and peacemaking thought Somalia constitution is based Federal system which was agreed by Somalis in 2004,when The Transitional Federal was established as one of the Transitional Federal Institutions (TFIs) of government as defined in the Transitional Federal Charter (TFC) adopted in November 2004 by the Transitional Federal Parliament (TFP).. According to According to the data collected from the respondents indicates that there is less

power sharing. The results showed that the relationship between federalism and peace in Mogadishu Somalia. As a result, it is recommended that orienting and teaching the community members and community leaders to understand federalism contributing on peacemaking.

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REFERENCE

- Prendergast, John & Colin Thomas-Jensen, 2007, 'Blowing the Horn,' *Foreign Affairs*, 86 (2): 59-74.
- Prunier, Gerard, 2006, 'A World of Conflict Since 9/11: The CIA Coup in Somalia,' *Review of African Political Economy*, 33 (110): 737-772.
- Ranger, Terrence, 2004, 'Nationalist Historiography, Patriotic History and the History of the Nation: the Struggle over the Past in Zimbabwe,' *Journal of Southern African Studies*, 30 (2): 215-234.
- Rothchild, Donald, 1964, 'East African Federation,' *Transition*, 12: 39-42.
- Rothchild, Donald, 1966, 'The Limits of Federalism: an Examination of Political Institutional Transfer in Africa,' *Journal of Modern African Studies*, 4 (3): 273-293.
- Rothchild, Donald, 1970, 'African Federations and the Diplomacy of Decolonization,' *Journal of Developing Areas*, 4 (4): 509-524.
- Samatar, Abdi Ismail, 2004, 'Ethiopian Federalism: Autonomy versus Control in the Somali Region,' *Third World Quarterly*, 25 (6): 1131-1154.
- Schiller, A. Arthur, 1953, 'Eritrea: Constitution and Federation with Ethiopia,' *American Journal of Comparative Law*, 2 (3): 375-383.
- Schmidt, Elizabeth, 2009, 'Anticolonial Nationalism in French West Africa: What Made Guinea Unique,' *African Studies Review*, 52 (2): 1-34.
- Scholler, Heinrich, 1994, 'The Ethiopian Federation of 1952: Obsolete Model or Guide for the Future,' in Peter Woodward & Murray Forsyth (eds.), *Conflict and Peace in the Horn of Africa. Federalism and Its Alternatives*, Dartmouth, Aldershot: 10-18.